
HADLEY V. BAXENDALE

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ABSTRACT

Hadley & Anor v Baxendale & Ors [1854] is an important contract law case in England. It establishes the leading rule for determining consequential damages resulting from a breach of contract: a breaching party is liable for all losses that the contracting parties should have anticipated, but not for any losses that the breaching party could not have anticipated based on the information available to him.

I. INTRODUCTION

- When the mill's crankshaft broke, Hadley owned and operated it. Hadley and Baxendale signed a contract for Hadley to deliver the shaft to an engineering firm on a specific date. Hadley failed to notify Baxendale that the mill was out of commission until the new shaft arrived.
- Hadley's mill remained inoperable as a result of Baxendale's failure to deliver the shaft to the engineering business on the agreed-upon date, resulting in lost profit.
- Hadley sued Baxendale, claiming that despite not informing Baxendale of the unusual circumstances, he was entitled to special damages in the form of lost profits.
- The court held that in order for a non-breaching party to recover damages arising out of any special circumstances, the special circumstances must be communicated to and known by all parties at the time of formation. Since Hadley failed to disclose his special circumstances to Baxendale, he was barred from the award of lost profits.
- The case was decided in the Court of Exchequer.
- Led by [Baron Sir Edward Hall Alderson](#)
- Judgment was delivered on: 23 February 1854.

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- Judges\Coram: Parke B, Alderson B, Platt B and Martin B.
- The **claimants** (Hadley et al), were **millers** operating a mill at the City Steam Mills in Gloucester.
- The **defendants** (Baxendale and Ors) were **common carriers** operating under the trade name Pickford & Co.

II. STATEMENT OF THE FACTS

The facts of Hadley v. Baxendale, an English case, involve a contract for carriage of a mill's broken component. Hadley was the owner of the City Steam Mills in Gloucester, along with his partners. The mill was involved in the steam-powered cleaning and processing of food grains into flour and bran. On one of the mill's operating days, the steam engine's crankshaft cracked, and the mill's production came to a standstill.

The proprietors of the mill contacted the engineering firm W. Joyce & Co., based in Greenwich, to manufacture a new crankshaft. The manufacturers sought the broken crankshaft to be sent to them as a reference for the new component.

Hadley, through his agent, contacted Baxendale, who was operating the common carrier Pickford & Co. Both parties agreed on a price for the shipping of the broken crankshaft and a deadline for the delivery was also agreed upon. Hadley did mention that it is extremely vital that the delivery is made within the deadline.

However, the consignment was rerouted through London, where the fractured crankshaft was kept in storage until it could be sent with other products bound for Greenwich. Several days after the deadline, the package arrived at the factory. The mill in Gloucester stayed closed the entire time. Hadley sustained a significant loss as a result of the mill's inactivity.

Hadley, enraged by his loss, sued Baxendale for damages, claiming that he had suffered losses as a result of the mill's non-operation, including possibly loss of goodwill and consumers.

III. ISSUE AND HOLDING

The **issue** related to the court defining the defendants' liability for consequential damages (lost profits) suffered by the plaintiffs due to the defendant's negligence resulting in a breach of contract.

Can damages for a party's breach include reasonably foreseeable damages and damages resulting from special circumstances if the special circumstances were not communicated at the time the contract was formed? **No.**

IV. RULE OF LAW OR LEGAL PRINCIPLE APPLIED

The *Hadley v Baxendale* case is an English decision establishing the rule for the determination of consequential damages in the event of a contractual breach. The *Hadley* case states that the breaching party must be held liable for all foreseeable losses. In other words, a breaching party cannot be held liable for damages that were not foreseeable after the contract. A contracting party will be held accountable for damages that arise naturally from the breach of contract and those that were in the reasonable contemplation of the parties at the time the contract was concluded.

Rule of *Hadley v. Baxendale* in Indian Contract Act, 1872

The rule of *Hadley v. Baxendale* is incorporated in the first proviso of Section 73 of the Indian Contract Act, of 1872. The Section, in full, states that:

“73. Compensation for loss or damage caused by breach of Contract– When a contract has been broken, the party who suffers by such breach is entitled to receive, from the party who has broken the contract, compensation for any loss or damage caused to him thereby, which naturally arose in the usual course of things from such breach, or which the parties knew, when they made the contract, to be likely to result from the breach of it.

Such compensation is not to be given for any remote and indirect loss or damage sustained by reason of the breach.

Compensation for failure to discharge obligations resembling those created by contract– When an obligation resembling those created by contract has been incurred and has not been discharged, any person injured by the failure to discharge it is entitled to receive the same compensation from the party in default, as if the person had contracted to discharge it and had broken his contract.

Explanation- In estimating the loss or damage arising from a breach of contract, the means which existed to remedy the inconvenience caused by the non-performance of the contract must be taken into account.”

The rule as embedded in Section 73 of the Indian Contract Act, 1872 had been used to decide several seminal cases by the Indian Judiciary.

The rule in *Hadley v. Baxendale* consists of two parts. On the breach of contract such damages can be recovered;

1. As may fairly and reasonably be considered arising naturally, i.e according to the usual course of things from such breach;
2. As may reasonably be supposed to have been in the contemplation of both the parties at the time they made the contract.

The **principle** stated in the two branches of the rule is virtually the rule of ”reasonable foresight”. The liability of the party making the breach of contract depends on the knowledge, imputed or actual, of the loss likely to arise in case of breach of contract.

- The first branch of the rule allows damages for the loss arising naturally, i.e. in the usual course of things from breach. The parties are deemed to know about the likelihood of such loss.
- The second branch of the rule deals with the recovery of more loss which results from the special circumstances of the case. Such loss is recoverable, if the possibility of the same was actually within the knowledge of the parties, particularly who makes a breach of the contract, at the time of making the contract.

V. JUDGMENT

The trial judge should instruct the jury not to consider lost profits in awarding damages.

The Court of Exchequer, led by Baron Sir Edward Hall Alderson, declined to allow *Hadley* to recover lost profits, holding that *Baxendale* could be held liable only for losses that were generally foreseeable, or if *Hadley* had mentioned his special circumstances in advance. The mere fact that a party is sending something to be repaired does not indicate that the party would lose profits if it is not delivered on time. The court suggested various

other circumstances under which Hadley could have entered into this contract that would not have presented such dire circumstances and noted that where special circumstances exist, provisions can be made in the contract voluntarily entered into by the parties to impose extra damages for a breach. Alderson B said the following.

- Now we think the proper rule in such a case as the present is this: *Where two parties have made a contract which one of them has broken, the damages which the other party ought to receive in respect of such breach of contract should be such as may fairly and reasonably be considered either arising naturally, i.e., according to the usual course of things, from such breach of contract itself or such as may reasonably be supposed to have been in the contemplation of both parties, at the time they made the contract, as the probable result of the breach of it.*

Now, if the special circumstances under which the contract was made were communicated by the plaintiffs to the defendants, and thus known to both parties, the damages resulting from the breach of such a contract, which they would reasonably contemplate, would be the amount of injury which would ordinarily follow from a breach of contract under these special circumstances so known and communicated. But, on the other hand, if these special circumstances were wholly unknown to the party breaking the contract, he, at the most, could only be supposed to have had in his contemplation the amount of injury which would arise generally, and in the great multitude of cases not affected by any special circumstances, from such a breach of contract. For, had the special circumstances been known, the parties might have specially provided for the breach of contract by special terms as to the damages in that case, and of this advantage, it would be very unjust to deprive them. Now the above principles are those by which we think the jury ought to be guided in estimating the damages arising out of any breach of contract... But it is obvious that, in the great multitude of cases of millers sending off broken shafts to third persons by a carrier under ordinary circumstances, such consequences would not, in all probability, have occurred, and these special circumstances were here never communicated by the plaintiffs to the defendants. It follows, therefore, that the loss of profits here cannot reasonably be considered such a consequence of the breach of contract as could have been fairly and reasonably contemplated by both parties when they made this contract.

VI. REASONING

At the time both parties entered into a contract, Hadley failed to tell Baxendale that any delay in shipping would result in Hadley's lost profits. Since Baxendale did not know of Hadley's special circumstances, that his mill was inoperable until the new shaft was delivered, the special circumstances were not reasonably foreseeable at the time the contract was formed.

The court of exchequer held that when one party breaches, the other party may recover damages that are reasonably foreseeable to both parties at contract formation. In addition, the non-breaching party may also recover damages arising out of any special circumstances so long as those circumstances are communicated to and known by all parties.

Here, Hadley's failure to disclose his special circumstances prevents him from recovering damages. Hadley never informed Pickford and Co. that his mill operation was entirely dependent on receiving a new shaft. The court points out that not all broken mill shafts render the mill inoperable resulting in lost profits. For example, some may have a temporary mill shaft for use when the broken one is out for repair. As a result, Baxendale is not liable for the damages arising out of Hadley's unknown circumstances.

VII. SIGNIFICANCE

Hadley v. Baxendale established a limitation on damages to those which naturally result from a breach and are reasonably contemplated by the contracting parties at contract formation. These damages are known as consequential damages.

The question before the Court of Exchequer was: whether Baxendale was liable to compensate for the non-operation of the mill.

The Bench held that Hadley could not recover the loss of profits from Baxendale as the shutting down of the mill was not contemplated as a consequence of the breach of contract by the breaching party. Hadley at the time of contracting did not mention that the mill will be non-operational till the new crankshaft is installed. A party cannot be expected to compensate for what he was not able to reasonably contemplate at the time of entering into a contract.

The judges pointed to alternate circumstances where also a mill owner could be sending his machinery for repair. There could be a spare for such a vital component so that the mill can remain functional or the mill could remain functional even without the component. Since the component was so vital to the mill's operation Hadley could have simply informed Baxendale of the nature of loss he stands to suffer if the delivery is not made on time. A reasonable man cannot be expected to come to that particular conclusion on his own.

Judge Sir Edward Hall Alderson laid down a general rule on damages in breach of contracts as:

“Where two parties have made a contract which one of them has broken, the damages which the other party ought to receive in respect of such breach of contract should be such as may fairly and reasonably be considered either arising naturally, i.e., according to the usual course of things, from such breach of contract itself or such as may reasonably be supposed to have been in the contemplation of both parties, at the time they made the contract, as the probable result of the breach of it.”

The rule of *Hadley v. Baxendale*, as stated above, talks about two types of damages: general damages and consequential or special damages.

The general damages are the ones that naturally arise from the breach of a contract. For example, if Raj contracts with Jai so that Raj will supply a certain quantity of food grains at a certain price on a specified date but fails to carry out the obligation. Then the general damages in such a case will equal the difference between the price that Jai has to pay for buying the same quantity of food grains on the specified date from another seller. So, the general damages in such a case will be the difference between the market price and the contract price of the goods.

General damages can easily be contemplated by the parties to a contract as the natural consequence of a failure to carry out the contractual obligations and can be claimed by the non-breaching party. But consequential damages are more difficult to quantify.

Each party entering a contract will have multiple interests which may not be often shared among them or known to the other side. In such cases, the breach of contract can have

several adverse impacts on the parties which though not arising directly from the breach may be consequential. Consequential damages aim to compensate for such remote losses.

According to the rule of *Hadley v. Baxendale*, consequential damages can be claimed by the non-breaching party only if both parties to the contract were aware of the possibility of such losses arising from the breach of contract. It is also to be noted that the rule on consequential damage is applied based on the knowledge of the parties at the time of contracting and according to the standard of a reasonable man.

The rule about consequential damages is effectively limiting the liability of the parties to a contract in the event of a breach of a contract. For example, consider the same situation we discussed in the case of general damages involving the delivery of food grains by A to B on a specified date. If the food grains were required by B as input to his food processing industry a failure of A to deliver the items on time will lead to halting of operation of the industry. A will be liable for the loss of profit only if B had informed him that the production would have to be stopped in case of a delay in the delivery of food grains.

The rule of *Hadley v. Baxendale* has wide acceptability and is incorporated in the contract laws of most common law jurisdictions. *Hadley v. Baxendale* requires that the court consider the foreseeable damages when evaluating damages for breach of contract (the foreseeability test).

Hadley v. Baxendale (1854) establishes the limits and boundaries of special damages that can be claimed by a party against another for breach of contract.

As it pertains to special damages or consequential losses, the court ruled that the extent of what can be claimed from a breaching party is what was in the reasonable contemplation of the parties upon entering into the contract.

LOSS OF PROFITS WAS NOT IN THE REASONABLE CONTEMPLATION OF BOTH PARTIES

In the *Hadley* case, the court of appeal highlighted that it was not reasonable for the defendants to reasonably contemplate the loss of profits claimed by *Hadley*. The mere fact that a carrier is asked to deliver something does not follow that profits could be lost

due to delays. In the case at the bar, the court found that the only facts communicated to Baxendale were that Hadley operated a mill and the article to be carried was a shaft from the mill. Such facts were not sufficient to allow Baxendale to reasonably contemplate the exposure to special damages when entering into the contract. The court then raises the question as to how Baxendale could have reasonably figured that profits at the mill were stopped by a delay in the delivery.

What was the principle laid down in Hadley v Baxendale?

In *Hadley v Baxendale* 1854, the court distinguishes between two types of damages:

1. Damages arising in the usual course of things
2. Damages that were in the reasonable contemplation of the parties upon conclusion of the contract

The court found that a breaching party must not be held liable for damages relating to special circumstances not known to the party breaching the terms of the contract.

In other words, if due to special circumstances, a party may suffer special damages, if the party communicates such special circumstances to the other party before signing the contract, then damages resulting from such special circumstances would have been known by the breaching party.

VIII. CONCLUSION

The rule of *Hadley v. Baxendale* limits the liabilities of the parties to a contract. In the event of a breach of the contract, according to the rule, the breaching party is to pay damages only for the losses naturally occurring from such breach and the losses which the parties could reasonably contemplate at the time of contracting.

The rule promotes contracting in commercial transactions as it limits the cost of a breach. The compensatory damages are to be paid only for the most proximate consequences of a breach. However, with the change in business practices and advancements in technology, the remotest consequences of a breach of contract can be predicted and mitigated. So, several writers believe that the rule of *Hadley v. Baxendale* is obsolete and needs revision. Despite the criticisms, the rule of *Hadley v. Baxendale* is still widely applicable

and acceptable in most English common law jurisdictions. On appeal, the Court of Exchequer did not award Hadley damages for lost profits.

The court concluded that Baxendale could not be held liable for damages that it could not have foreseen when he entered into the contract.

DAMAGES ARE LIMITED TO WHAT WAS IN THE REASONABLE CONTEMPLATION OF BOTH PARTIES

The damages a non-breaching party may claim should be limited to those in the contemplation of the parties upon entering into the contract. In the court's view, Hadley could have entered into a contract in a different way by including contractual provisions allowing for additional damages in the event of a breach or notifying Baxendale of his special circumstances. If Hadley had informed Baxendale of his special circumstances and potential for loss of profits before signing the contract, then the potential for his lost profits would have been known to Baxendale and would have been in the parties' contemplation.

